

Using Computer Assisted Language Learning for English Language Teaching: An Adaptive Approach with its Current Development

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ABSTRACT

In this modern era of information and technology, CALL is widely regarded as a technique for language teaching and learning. When it comes to learning languages, computers are increasingly being used to aid in the teaching and learning process, particularly for English language teaching (ELT). This is known as "computer-assisted language learning." Using CALL can be more productive in language teaching and learning. When it comes to teaching and learning, ICT is commonly regarded as a tool, but there are still a number of problems with effectively using CALL. Nevertheless, a certain level of sensitivity and knowledge of how the program might be utilised effectively is required for its incorporation into language training via CALL. The goal of this research is to examine the impact of computer-assisted language learning in the context of English language teaching and learning, specifically the types of activities that are more likely to be successful. There is an outline of how computers have evolved in the classroom. Discussing the benefits and drawbacks of using CALL in the classroom will be done. Moving forward, this paper will cover a variety of computer-based learning activities for English language training with a focus on CALL, the future of CALL, and how it might be further developed in the context of today's rapidly expanding technological landscape. This article will also discuss the complexity of CALL and its adaptive approach with respect to individuals' understanding, as well as the contribution of CALL and its success in teaching English and aiding language learning.

KEYWORDS: *Computer assisted language learning (CALL), English language teaching (ELT), English as a Second Language (ESL), (Information and Communication Technology (ICT)*

INTRODUCTION

Because of the rapid spread of English through information and technology, business, and education, English has now established itself as a global language and has played a significant part in the communications of every nation on earth. English is considered to be one of the most important foreign languages taught in Indian schools and academic institutions. However, their English skills (LSW) as measured by national tests (e.g., TOEFL, IELTS, CAE, CPE) have not improved despite the fact that all parties concerned have been working and giving their maximum efforts to improve English teaching and English proficiency. This inadequate performance of students in English at all levels demonstrates that, despite the efforts of all stakeholders, English

language teaching in India has not made satisfactory progress in recent years. As a result, educators, teachers, administrators, and curriculum developers must pay immediate attention in order to improve English language teaching and learning in India. They must be keen to detect the most appropriate strategy for teaching English to second language learners in order for their English performance to match the demands of the international community and for them to be able to completely and successfully integrate into the global community. Because of the wider adoption of computer and educational technologies in today's world, computers have infiltrated and profoundly touched every aspect of our lives, particularly in the realm of communication.

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According to this development, there is a greater need for English language proficiency in the workplace. As a result of this move, English has been made a mandatory subject in India's secondary schools, with a concentration on self-regulated learning, independent work, as well as innovations and new technology in the field of English language instruction. There can be little doubt that this situation has had an impact on the entire spectrum of English language instruction, from the aims and practices of teaching and evaluation, through teacher education and professional development. This paper examines the notion of call in general, as well as offers a worldwide picture of how CALL originated and is important for language teaching. It also discusses the benefits and drawbacks of incorporating CALL into the effectiveness of English language learning initiatives in general. Specifically, it is discussed what types of educational activities are most likely to be successful when computer technology is used in English language instruction in India, as well as future research and the scope of CALL for English Language Teaching and Learning.

Literature Review: This study is concerned with using CALL in English language learning to understand how it works. There is no doubt that the last century has witnessed marvelous and path breaking innovations, achievements, and breakthroughs in all spheres of knowledge. A brilliant example is computer technology, which has changed the dissemination of knowledge and thus impacts all sections of human life. Some related literature, such as Research on ICT's role in supporting self-advancement and learning for students with special educational needs was reviewed by Williams et al. (2006) in preparation for an extensive study on the topic. Another researcher, Abu Seileek A. (2013), The Effect of CALL methods and tolls for English Learners, explores the need for CALL-inlanguage teaching. Edgar, R. (2017). Computer Assisted Language Teaching: Learning without Dust. The Journal of Computing in Higher Education.

How and why computers should be employed in CALL has become a key point of contention (Beatty, 2010). For this reason, new fields of inquiry are emerging that focus on concerns of autonomy (Chik& Ho, 2017), identity (Chen, 2013; Lam, 2000; Schreiber, 2015), group (Gao, 2007), and intercultural competency (Gao, 2007), among other things (Hull et al., 2010; Thorne, 2010). According to Lam (2000), Almon, a Hong Kong-born immigrant living in the United States, was studied in terms of how he communicated in English online. As a second-language learner (ESL), Almon was frustrated with

his lack of proficiency in English and felt ostracized from the classroom. A worldwide online Japanese pop (J-pop) group allowed him to speak in English with other J-pop fans from around the world, despite his limited ability to read or write Japanese. Almon's ability to speak a second language and use computers helped him overcome the isolation and marginalization he felt in ESL schools. He was able to negotiate a new status as a user of English all over the world. Such learner-centered research has shown a greater diversity of views and lenses for CALL researchers to determine effectiveness is no more the only determinant to be studied.

Background of CALL (Computer Assisted language Learning): CALL has its roots in the introduction of technology into language learning in the mid-1950s. In Davies and Higgins (1982), p. 3, they say that computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is a subset of the general term "computer-assisted instruction." This is because CALL is a subset of the general term "computer assisted instruction." "CALL is a subset of CAI. Language teachers, on the other hand, are more likely to favor a method that puts the student at the center of instruction. As a result, CALI began to be phased out in favor of CALL, which emphasizes learning over instruction." "The search for and study of applications of the computer in language teaching and learning" was characterized as "CALL" by Levy (1997). It encompasses a wide range of ICTs, apps, and teaching and learning techniques for foreign languages.

Despite the fact that computers have been around since the first part of the twentieth century, they were not used for academic purposes until the late 1960s. The emergence of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) began in the 1970s as a result of advances in research towards the use of technology for linguistic purposes and the creation of favorable language learning environments. Initially evolved in the United States in the 1960s, computer-based introductory courses were considered foundational initiatives in CALL and were called computer-assisted instruction (CAI). Both in academic systems and in people's homes, the 1980s saw the widespread use of computers become more common. Since the early 1980s, computers have made their way into a large number of educational institutions. CALL technology has also become more widely available to consumers in the last few years (Ittelson, 2000). As low-cost technology and large storage devices, such as optical videodiscs and compact discs, have become more widely available, instructional technologists now have more instruments with which to do their

jobs. Compressed disk storage devices, such as encyclopedias and motion pictures, are being used to preserve vast volumes of data. CALL centers equipped with computers and software such as CD-ROM, CD-I, or videodiscs allow students who are interested in a particular topic to first scan an electronic encyclopedia. The history of CALL, according to War Schauer and Healey (1998), can be split into three different phases: behavioristic CALL, communicative CALL, and integrative CALL. Each phase refers to a specific approach to pedagogy in the classroom.

Types:

- Call Specific Software- CD Rom, web-based interaction etc.
- Generic Software- word processor, power point, and excel etc.
- Web based - dictionaries, online encyclopedia, wen quest, blog, etc.
- Computer mediated Communication - Facebook, email, forum etc.

ELT (English Language Teaching): The emergence of English Language Teaching (ELT) has come a long way from 1880, when just 60% of primary schools in India employed English as their language of instruction. After 1940, the grammar-translation approach was in full bloom, and English spread haphazardly in educational and business circles. Structural linguistics made its way into Indian schools in the form of practice and learning in the 1970s. Around this time, English became the language of instruction for all professional courses, as well as the language of reference in libraries and for self-study. Indians learned English as a first language in the 1940s, but only in the 1980s did ELT become a separate field of study.

ELT paradigms in these nations began to incorporate language laboratories in 1985, as opposed to the 1940s in the United States. Most classrooms had CALI, or Computer Assisted Language Instruction, in 1960, but it only arrived in the Indian classroom in 1985. In other places, CALL, or Computer Assisted Language Learning, is now being used, keeping in view the importance of fast-growing technological advancements, political discourse, translation, etc. Moreover, the importance of ELT has been strongly recognized at a global level as 'lingua franca' due to its linguistic diversity. So far as ELT is concerned, it is being taught for different purposes both at national and international level to cater to the learner's needs, such as:

- ESL (English as second language)
- EFL (English as foreign language)
- ESP (English for Specific purposes)

Use of Computer/Internet in Teaching Learning:

Technology plays a very important role in transferring knowledge from one end to the other. A computer is a device that is capable of processing information at high speeds and with high accuracy. Computers interpret information in many different ways, including assisting in the creation of the information itself, presenting, collecting, recognizing, and transmitting information to and from other computers. On a broad level, they are able to comprehend and absorb numbers, words, still or moving images, and noises. People's ways of working, learning, communicating, and playing have all been transformed by the computer. It is utilised as a study aid by students, teachers, and research scientists all around the world, as well as by people at home for a variety of purposes, including studying, working, and entertaining. Additionally, the internet broadens students' horizons, gives systematic confirmation of the use of language competency, and serves as a powerful stimulant for the overall language learning activities. Inexperienced users may be daunted by the vast amount of information and resources accessible, even while the internet is a great resource for obtaining full-text newspapers, magazines, journals, scholarly works, and even novels. There are several tools available to help you locate the information you are looking for, including search engines, repositories, libraries, and online encyclopedias (Encarta, 2000). When teachers have access to all of this material thanks to the internet, they can be even more creative and up to date, says Gray (who was cited in Sperling, 1998).

Here are some CALL tools and their uses, with their advantages and disadvantages. **Webinar:** One can present his idea with the help of the web, which means the instructor or teacher can be present from anywhere. It is not necessary to be present in class, so somewhere. It makes it easy for language teaching. And nowadays, it is being used very frequently in teaching, so it can be used in ELT as well, which is a part of computer assisted language learning.

PPT-Like I am presenting my ideas with the help of PPT. In the very same way, it is being used in language teaching, especially in the English language, because it's quite challenging for any teacher to carry many books at one point of time, so with the help of a computer, we can present or show different ideas at the same point of time. It makes language teaching easy and affective for language teaching.

Pictorial presentation: In language teaching, images play a very important role in making students understandable, so it's not necessary that an ELT teacher be good enough to draw pictures. With the

help of a computer, it is very easy to do this task and makes language teaching affective.

Dictionaries: during vocabulary teaching, it is very challenging for the teacher to remember thousands or hundreds of words at one point of time, but with the help of computer assisted language, we can show them many vocabularies at the same time and we can allot them to learn. Online PDFT his is the software

Pros and Cons of CALL:

Pros	Cons
Can cover large number of students	Require a computer engineer and Expensive
Individualization	infrastructure
Learn more and more rapidly	Negative impact on some language skill due to overuse (reading writing speaking)
Economize time and effort	Required trained instructor
Minimize work load	Require prior knowledge of computer skill
Guided and repetitive practice in multiple modes with feedback	Computers cannot handle unforeseen changes
More easy and effective than traditional methods of language Teaching	Inability to handle unexpected situations imperfect current CALL programs

The Impact of the Internet on English Language Teaching (ELT) Before and After the Internet Era:

To understand the impact of computers and technology on English language teaching, we must understand how it developed and how it is used for language teaching, step by step. Before the Internet, technology in ELT could be perceived in one of two ways. Initially, computer assisted language learning (CALL) emerged and focused on the technology's educational technologies. The computer was utilised by the students to improve and practice their English. CALL is still used today, but prior to the Internet, narrow text-based services piqued the interest of both learners and eager practitioners; of course, this piqued interest has faded for many people who use computers on a daily basis. The use of computers to assist in the knowledge of what makes up the English language and how it operates was a second point of view. Sinclair (1987) and others pioneered corpus linguistics and the inclusion of lexis as a curriculum item in the 1980s, and similar work is still going on today. According to Winsor (1990), Winsor (1990) argues that the frequency of study, which began with written language, but has since expanded to include spoken language, has had a significant impact on the profession. It has helped us discover the most useful terminology to teach and has aided in the creation of a lexical curriculum. Form-based terms may now be examined, which has given us new insights into the language we teach. For students and teachers, there has been an increase in the number and variety of publications focused on real-world usage, rather than what a typical grammar book dictate. In the

development of new terminology, the Internet (of which CMC is a key component) is altering the English language, but it does so due to the medium itself and the influence of its users (Crystal, 2001). To give you an idea of how rapidly the English language has changed, consider the verbs "email," "text," "boot," "chat," "surf," "bookmark," "e-shop," "Google," and so on. Basically, the Internet is altering the language we use. Terms like "Netspeak" and "Netiquette" are emerging to describe the standards that surround the medium's proper use on the Internet. This rapidly changing language lacks a significant history to guide curriculum designers and ELT practitioners. There is no need for punctuation rules to be adhered to in emails. In this medium, typos and misspellings are more permissible, based on the circumstances (Asian EFL Journal, 2009).

CALL's future in relation to its past: There is a long history behind the term "CALL," which we use in reference to an extensive range of technology and methodologies linked to teaching and learning second or foreign languages. As computers become less apparent and more pervasive, so do they. Different sorts of technology, rather than merely the usually identified computer, are now the primary focus. Scholars have also adopted the term "technology-enhanced language learning" (TELL) as a more inclusive phrase to describe this type of learning. AR and VR, two relatively new forms of immersive virtual reality, have the potential to revolutionize the way people learn languages. It is possible to allow learners to connect with linguistic environments in real life by adding additional information to the

environment, for example. The fact that language itself is multi-faceted may make AR a much more effective tool for language training than the dullness of a textbook. multilayered and sophisticated, helping learners to better connect real-life experiences with language learning. Programs such as this one was developed by Vazquez and his colleagues (2017) to help students acquire words in contexts that are rich in media and rich in technology. If you don't have the time or money to travel abroad to fully immerse yourself in the target language's motherland, virtual reality may be a better option for you. Some language learners may benefit from it as well. Studying Chinese characters in VR can make students more excited and interested. AR and VR will likely see more research and practice in the coming years. Mobile assisted language learning (MALL) is an emerging field that has high expectations (Stockwell, 2016). Because cellphones are so widely available and portable, anyone can use them to learn a language at any time and any place. Also, location-based content on mobile devices provides context-sensitivity (Han, 2019). Connecting what you're doing in your day-to-day life with the languages you wish to learn can be done with the help of AR. With the introduction of smartphones and their potential for language acquisition, MALL is an exciting new field worth exploring. We expect AI will be widely used in all parts of life, including language teaching and learning. Intelligent CALL refers to applying AI approaches to CALL (Schulze, 2008). By combining AI with captivating technologies like AR and VR, we may one day be able to interact with our AI assistants as if they were real people. It is possible for AI helpers to provide individualized training or even prolonged language practice to help students better understand their feelings and needs. CA research will grow as a result of this connection between AI and learners.

An Adaptive Approach to CALL: Recognizing and Addressing Complexity: The related study's research topics and context heavily influence the choice of theoretical lenses and methodological approaches. Still, it's fantastic to see a variety of approaches to CALL being used. In an ideal world, these various points of view will continue to add to CALL's growing body of knowledge. This study of prior CALL practice and philosophy has led me to the conclusion that CALL, structured or unstructured, is a wildly unpredictable and dynamic process. Learning is a unique experience for each person, just like learning itself. There is no single best method or tool for learning or teaching languages. Instead of generalizing, focus should be on the variety of particular paths. Learner corpora that collect different

kinds of L2 developments, as Godwin-Jones (2018) points out, can help discover variance and provide different methods and other ways for different learners to "make feasible personalized learning environments." (Godwin-Jones, 2018). Ecological and complexity theories, which look at the individual, growth, and system as a whole, are useful tools for researchers today as they try to understand CALL in its current form. An in-depth look at an individual's growth can be found in case studies. If we combine them, we will get a richer picture of what it's like to be a CALL learner. The use of narrative methods (such as diaries, reflections, and interviews) can provide a more in-depth look at people's attitudes, beliefs, and viewpoints in certain situations. In order to better understand the dynamics of the development process, ethnographic methods (online and in person) are used to collect and monitor the data (e.g., recordings of CALL activities). Learner-created artefacts (e.g., a student's digital output) are useful for analyzing learning outcomes and the formation of personal identities. Data triangulation allows an impartial and comprehensive analysis of an individual language learner's CALL learning trajectory with different data sources. To prepare for the new environment of CALL, we will no doubt revisit our conceptual models and methodological approaches. The future of CALL appears to be moving toward self-direction, aided by artificial intelligence and interactive technologies. The most front-line technology will not be helpful if a learner doesn't use it. Therefore, perhaps an autonomous learning theoretical lens would be a better fit for CALL. For example, artificial intelligence-assisted augmented reality and virtual reality (AR and VR) could assist future language students in better integrating information by providing them with a gateway that integrates what they learn with what they experience in the current world. We should continue to embrace and exploit this technology.

Objective of This paper: The main aim of the proposed work is to identify the impact of CALL in ELT and to explore the best approach of CALL with respect to English language teaching and learning purposes. It will also explore the development of CALL through the rapid transformation of technology and its positive and negative outcomes, and whether using computers in learning may be beneficial for EFL/ESL learners. Researchers and government officials will benefit greatly from this information since it will help them better understand how to manage English-language programmes. The second objective is to address the complexity of CALL for English language teaching and how it should be adopted for teaching and learning purposes in order to

make the use of CALL more effective for both teachers and students, as well as administrators, to reap the greatest possible benefits from using this technology.

Significance of the Study: CALL for English Language Instruction in ELT may help ELT programme heads and administrators with policies and procedures that guide the training faculty on the use of technology in ELT programmes. Further, it may affect decisions concerning the purchase and maintenance of software and hardware. In addition, identification of the skills required to use CALL in an EFL/ESL classroom could assist in the selection and training of prospective and established teacher educators. In fact, language teachers need to know different factors like recent developments in the field of CALL and its future direction, as well as different adaptative approaches to CALL that can help them meaningfully use CALL, which has been proven to be an effective and practical tool for both the trainers and trainees.

Conclusion: When it comes to augmenting or removing direct student-teacher interaction, CALL has emerged as a compelling alternative to established methods like the language laboratory or audiotape-based self-study, among others. It is the primary goal of this paper to highlight and explain the possible function that CALL systems might play in language classes as a significant teaching aid or tool of education by providing examples. A thorough discussion of why CALL is significant in the area of language teaching and learning is provided in this paper, which also covers the creation of CALL-in language teaching, teacher and learner's expectations, programme design, and evaluation. The advantages and disadvantages, as well as the possibilities and risks, of both functions, are also talked about. This is especially true in the context of ELT. In reality, technology and computers have revolutionized human life, so it has compelled teachers and researchers to consider the implication of CALL-in language teaching. As a matter of fact, technology bridges the lacuna between the learner and teacher, both from material and teaching aid perspectives. Therefore, it is imperative to advocate the need for the inclusion of CALL in the existing English learning system in order to economise and felicitate the teaching and learning effort. As a result, teachers must decide whether or not to incorporate technology into their language learning environments, and they must focus on ensuring that they are comfortable with the technological choices available and their appropriateness for specific learning objectives,

before implementing these technologies and taking advantage of their unique features.

Modern technological and pedagogical advancements have made it possible to integrate computers into language learning environments. Students can be immersed in a variety of linguistic environments through the use of multimedia technologies that incorporate speech recognition software. A massive language database can be used by students to investigate how language is used in real-world situations. It also allows users to create text - based content and multimedia content as well as publish their work to a global audience through the platform. This study also makes an attempt to inspire all English teachers to make the most of the opportunities presented by technological advancements in their classrooms. After receiving extensive exposure to language input through legitimate activities and tasks, as well as increased sensitivity to language practice, learners should be able to accurately determine and exercise their language skills, from which they can anticipate different CALL tasks. Once this is accomplished, it is expected that the students will be able to draw valid conclusions from particular situations. For English learners, it is essential that they are able to consistently use, experiment with, and evaluate suitable and relevant CALL activities in order to improve their English proficiency and develop their English language skills, which are the ultimate goals of language acquisition.

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